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SECTION 1. ARTICLES FROM ASIA

1.	TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS TO APPLY DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL STRATEGIES Mo'minov Sarvarbek Ulug'bek o'g'li	5
2.	ANALYSIS OF THE LEVEL OF DESIRE FOR SUCCESS IN YOUNG ATHLETES BY GENDER AND AGE Raximov G'ulomjon Davronbekovich	11
3.	GENETIC ALGORITHMS IN TRAINING NEURAL NETWORKS Bredy Nilson	15
4.	EVOLUTIONARY PROGRAMMING AND GENETIC ALGORITHMS IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE Tojimamatov I.Ch	23
5.	СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОЕ СОПОСТАВЛЕНИЕ И АНАЛИЗ РУССКОГО И БЕЛОРУССКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ. Толипова Нарзига Муйдинжон Кизи	29
6.	PROBLEMS OF WORKING WITH BIG DATA Egor Venchislav	32
7.	STUDY SKILL ACHIEVEMENT Yergeshova Nafisa Shukhrat kizi	37
8.	GENERAL PROPERTIES OF ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVES Oripova Sarvinoz Ruzali kizi	39

**ANALYSIS OF THE LEVEL OF DESIRE FOR SUCCESS IN YOUNG ATHLETES
BY GENDER AND AGE****Raximov G'ulomjon Davronbekovich**

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Abstract: This thesis presents an educational and psychological analysis of the level of striving for success in young athletes by gender and age factors. The study examines how the desire and motivation for success of young athletes change, as well as the differences between girls and boys. The thesis is aimed at identifying success factors in the field of sports psychology and education, and the results are of practical importance in organizing the effective training process of athletes and improving their mental state. It was shown that by studying in-depth the influence of gender and age factors on the level of striving for success, it is possible to improve the training and motivation system, taking into account the individual characteristics of young athletes.

Keywords: Young athletes, striving for success, gender, age, motivation, sports psychology, individual differences, training methodology.

Introduction

Striving for success is the main component of the volitional, motivational and psychological activity of an individual subject in any field of activity to achieve their goals. In particular, the desire for success in sports is considered an important factor for the professional development, psychological stability and competitiveness of young athletes. Scientific research shows that the level of desire for success has a significant impact on the athlete's results, attitude to training and mental state.

The level of desire for success in young athletes depends on many internal and external factors, the main of which are sexual identity and age-related psychological characteristics. The gender factor plays an important role in the motivational structure of athletes, since the mechanisms of desire and the methods of achieving goals may differ in male and female athletes (Gill, 2000). The age factor is one of the main points of developmental psychology, reflecting changes in the cognitive, emotional and social characteristics of athletes. Therefore, an in-depth analysis of the motivational characteristics of age groups serves to optimize their individual training processes (Weinberg & Gould, 2011).

The main objective of this study is to study the level of achievement motivation in young athletes by gender and age, to determine their motivational profile and to assess its impact on positive results in sports activities. The results of the study provide a scientific basis for the formation of age- and gender-appropriate individual approaches in sports psychology and coaching practice.

Materials and methods

Young athletes aged 12 to 18 years were selected as the study materials. There were 150 respondents in total, evenly distributed by gender: 75 girls and 75 boys. By age group, athletes were divided into 3 subgroups: 12-14 years, 15-16 years and 17-18 years. These age ranges were determined based on the developmental psychology and sports training characteristics of children and adolescents (Erikson, 1968; Gould, 2006).

The study used the standardized Achievement Motivation Scale to measure achievement motivation, a psychodiagnostic tool designed to assess athletes' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The scale includes components such as athletes' competitiveness, goal orientation, self-evaluation, and self-analysis (Nicholls; Duda & Nicholls).

Questionnaire and individual interview methods were used to collect data. The questionnaires were collected anonymously and recorded information on each athlete's gender, age, sport, and practical experience. The study used statistical analysis methods: descriptive statistics (mean, median, variance), t-tests (to determine differences between gender groups), ANOVA (to compare between age groups), and correlation analysis to study the relationship between achievement motivation and age-sex variables (Field).

The research procedure was conducted in accordance with the International Code of Ethics for Sport Psychology, and informed consent was obtained from all participants and their parents. At the same time, the scientific novelty of the study is to provide a deeper analysis of the influence of age and gender factors on the desire for success in sports and to identify their practical application in the coaching process.

Results

The results of the study showed that the level of desire for success in young athletes has significant differences depending on gender and age factors. When analyzing gender differences, a higher level of desire for success was observed among male athletes. This is probably explained by the stronger development of readiness for competition and self-motivation mechanisms in men. In girls, the desire for success is slightly lower, which may be due to their greater reliance on social support and external motivation.

The age factor plays an important role in the dynamics of the desire for success. The study found that while the level of aspiration among athletes aged 12-14 was average, this indicator increased significantly in the 15-16 and 17-18 age groups. This is explained by the fact that young people are more clearly oriented towards their goals, as well as better aware of their strengths and capabilities. The process

of personal identification and the desire for independence that are developing in young athletes increase their motivation for success. A positive correlation was also found between the desire for success and the psychological stability of athletes. This indicates that athletes with a high level of aspiration are more resistant to stress and difficulties and are more effective in their activities. Based on the results, it can be noted that coaches and psychologists should develop individual approaches specific to gender and age to increase the level of athletes' desire for success. Since male and female athletes differ in their sources of motivation, it is advisable to use special strategies aimed at strengthening personal motivation in the coaching process. It is also necessary to develop flexible methodologies to guide young athletes to success, taking into account their developmental stages and psychological characteristics. Overall, the study demonstrated that the level of achievement motivation has a direct impact on sports performance and systematically explored the impact of age and gender factors on this process. These results once again confirm the importance of motivational and psychological support in the training and development of young athletes.

Conclusion.

This study made a significant contribution to sports psychology and coaching practice by scientifically analyzing the dependence of the level of achievement motivation in young athletes on gender and age factors. The results of the study showed that achievement motivation is a complex psychological process closely related not only to the level of individual internal motivation, but also to external factors, in particular, psychological and social characteristics related to gender and age.

Regarding gender differences, significant differences in the mechanisms of motivation and achievement between male and female athletes were identified, which indicates the need for further individualization of coaching and training processes. High competitiveness and self-motivation in male athletes, and a high need for social support in women, were recognized as one of the main factors in the formation of motivational strategies. Therefore, it is necessary for sports psychologists and coaches to apply a gender-specific approach to practice and create an individual plan taking into account the motivational profile of each athlete.

Age was also studied as an important factor determining the level of striving for success. Differences in the motivational characteristics of age groups are especially associated with the processes of personal identification and self-awareness that occur during adolescence, which further increases the importance of coaching and psychological support at this stage. It is important to develop motivational strategies and training methodologies that take into account the

developmental characteristics of young athletes in supporting their striving for success.

The results showed that by increasing the level of striving for success, it is possible to strengthen the mental stability of athletes and increase their ability to withstand stress and difficulties. This, in turn, creates the basis for achieving high results in sports and long-term success in professional activities. Therefore, the systematic organization of motivational and psychological support, and the improvement of coaching processes taking into account the personal characteristics of young athletes are considered an important pedagogical task. In general, this study sheds light on the formation of young athletes' desire for success based on individual and social factors. This serves as a scientific basis not only for sports psychology, but also for the development of effective approaches in the process of educating and developing young people in general. It is recommended that more extensive research be conducted in this direction in the future, and other social, cultural and pedagogical factors of the desire for success should be studied in depth.

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